

MEDICAL SCIENCES

SECONDARY DENTAL ARCH DEFORMATION IN CHILDREN DURING THE MIXED DENTITION PERIOD

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Abstract

Objective: To assess the prevalence of secondary dental arch deformation in children during the mixed dentition period.

Materials and Methods: A dental examination was conducted on 505 children aged 6 to 14 years attending a school in Tashkent. Among them, 232 boys (45.9%) and 273 girls (54.1%) were examined. From this group, 152 children (30.1%) with secondary dental arch deformations were identified as the main group, including 73 boys (48.03%) and 79 girls (51.97%). These children underwent a comprehensive set of diagnostic, therapeutic, and preventive measures.

Results: The findings revealed that various factors contributed to the development of secondary dental arch deformations in children during the mixed dentition period. These factors included chewing dysfunction (unilateral chewing), speech disorders, biting foreign objects, mouth breathing, early loss of primary molars, and others.

Conclusion: The prevalence of anomalies and deformations in children during the mixed dentition period is very high (63.9%). Children with dental anomalies and deformations of the teeth, dental arches, and occlusion should be referred to appropriate specialists for consultation and treatment.

Keywords: children, mixed dentition, secondary dental and dental arch deformations, preventive measures

Anomalies and deformations of the dentoalveolar system (DAS) in children and adolescents rank among the leading causes of dental morbidity. Dentoalveolar anomalies and secondary deformations in children and adolescents disrupt the functions of the dentoalveolar system, complicate prosthetic treatment, negatively affect periodontal tissue health, occlusion formation, facial aesthetics, and overall psycho-emotional well-being.

There is a clear correlation: the older the age group, the greater the number of children requiring treatment, while the need for preventive orthodontic measures decreases. Timely diagnosis and effective treatment of dentoalveolar anomalies and deformations remain a pressing issue. Therefore, the greatest focus should be placed on implementing the most effective treatment and prevention methods during the primary and mixed dentition stages in children.

Objective: To assess the prevalence of secondary dental arch deformation in children during the mixed dentition period.

Materials and Methods

A dental examination was conducted on 505 children aged 6 to 14 years attending a school in Tashkent. Among them, 232 boys (45.9%) and 273 girls (54.1%) were examined. From this group, 152 children (main group) with secondary dental arch deformation were identified, including 73 boys (48.03%) and 79 girls (51.97%). These children underwent a comprehensive set of diagnostic, therapeutic, and preventive measures.

The examination results were grouped by age categories corresponding to the stages of occlusion development. The main group was conditionally divided into two subgroups: 1st subgroup – early mixed dentition (6-9 years old): 70 children (46.1%), including 31 boys and 39 girls; 2nd subgroup – late mixed dentition (10-14 years old): 82 children (53.9%), including 42 boys and 40 girls.

The comparison group, serving as a control, included 69 children in the mixed dentition period with physiological occlusion and no anomalies or deformations of the dentoalveolar system. This group consisted of 28 boys (40.6%) and 41 girls (59.4%), selected during a routine dental screening of schoolchildren in Tashkent.

The diagnosis of secondary dental and dental arch deformations was based on: medical history, clinical examination, anthropometric analysis of the face and oral cavity, cephalometric radiography (TRG) and panoramic radiography (OPG) of the jaws, biometric analysis of diagnostic dental models.

Research Results

The results of clinical and additional studies of the dentoalveolar system revealed that secondary dentoalveolar deformations were present in 152 children, accounting for 30.09% of the total number of children with mixed dentition. It is important to note that some children exhibited multiple dentoalveolar deformations, and they were classified into groups based on the severity of the dominant deformation.

The most frequently detected dental arch deformations included: secondary edentulism – 30 children (5.94%), early extraction of primary teeth – 24 children (4.75%), unworn cusps of primary teeth – 20 children (3.96%), dentoalveolar elongation – 21 children (4.16%)

Early loss of primary and permanent chewing teeth in children aged 14 years during the mixed dentition period often led to mesial shifting of posterior teeth, which subsequently caused crowding of anterior teeth.

In cases of symmetric primary edentulism, children generally did not exhibit severe cosmetic abnormalities. However, midline deviations and occlusal disorders were frequently observed.

After a comprehensive dental examination, all selected children underwent therapeutic dental treatment. The interventions depended on the etiology and pathogenesis of the secondary dentoalveolar deformations, their location and severity, and included: tooth or root extractions, selective grinding of unworn cusps in primary teeth, orthodontic correction of tooth and dental arch positions, prosthetic restoration of partial dental arch defects

Prevalence and Treatment Approaches

The examination of schoolchildren in Tashkent and the analysis of the collected data demonstrated a high prevalence of anomalies and deformations in children with mixed dentition, reaching 63.9%. However, despite the high incidence of dental anomalies and malocclusions, the level of dental and orthodontic care provided to these children remained low, at only 6.93%.

All examined children were referred to specialists for consultation and treatment based on: the condition of hard and soft tissues of the oral cavity, the presence of speech defects, the degree of nasal breathing impairment

Among the examined children: 86 underwent oral sanitation, 12 received temporary partial removable dentures, 19 were fitted with various orthodontic appliances, 38 were prescribed myogymnastics, 15 under-

went grinding of primary tooth cusps, 11 received frenulum corrections, 14 had primary tooth roots extracted, 8 underwent sanitation of ENT organs

Conclusion

The prevalence of anomalies and deformations in children with mixed dentition in Tashkent reaches 65.5%. Various functional disorders were identified in 304 children (60.2%) out of 505 examined, including: chewing dysfunction (unilateral chewing) – 57 children (18.8%), speech disorders – 64 children (21.1%), biting foreign objects – 46 children (15.1%), mouth breathing – 38 children (12.5%), early loss of primary molars – 47 children (15.5%), primary edentulism – 21 children (6.9%), unworn cusps of primary canines – 62 children (20.4%)

These factors predisposed 152 children (30.1%) to the development of secondary dental arch deformations during the mixed dentition period.

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